

PathFinder's High-Resolution Pan-European Forest Structure Maps: An Integration of Earth Observation and National Forest Inventory Data

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Abstract

Using the PathFinder mapping and estimation platform, pan-European forest resource maps for 18 forest attributes were produced. Apart from the modifications in datasets and methodology reported in this document, the approach followed Miettinen & Breidenbach et al. (2025). Here, we report the results of the map uncertainty analyses and provide technical details of the output products. Details on how to access the maps are also provided. Further information and results from the PathFinder project are available at <https://pathfinder-heu.eu/>.

Materials and methods

The production of the European-wide maps followed the process described in Miettinen & Breidenbach et al. (2025) (referred to as initial demonstration), with three major exceptions.

First, the Copernicus tree cover density and forest type products were not used as explanatory variables. Instead, environmental variables were used including: 1) a digital elevation model (DEM) (<https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>) and 2) climate data (1981-2010) including mean annual temperature and precipitation (Karger et al. 2017, 2018; downloaded from <https://chelsea-climate.org/>).

Second, the way the National Forest Inventory (NFI) plots were used was entirely changed. A fully automated processing approach was introduced, aiming to demonstrate the feasibility for operational map production. For each of 740 Sentinel processing tiles covering Europe, a tile feature bank was created based on the 1500 plots that were geographically closest to the tile centre.

Third, error metrics were calculated for each tile feature bank separately. Using the 1500 plots that were used in k-NN mapping, the error metrics were calculated using leave-one-out cross-validation. Error metrics were calculated with equations provided in Miettinen & Breidenbach et al. (2025). It is important to note that for tiles without NFI sample plots, the error metrics were calculated within the tile feature bank containing the closest 1500 NFI sample plots, located fully outside the tile in question. Because the forest structure represented by the closest feature bank is necessarily different than the actual local condition, the error metrics will be more or less biased for these tiles. Tiles without plots are for that reason indicated with a hashed pattern in all the Figures that follow.

Table 1 lists the 18 mapped attributes and some key characteristics. Year 2020 was considered the main demonstration year as the field reference data had a better temporal match with the 2020 Sentinel-2 data than the 2024 data. Temporal consistency with the plots was considered important for comparison with the estimates produced purely from the field plots using nFIESTA (Adolt et al. 2018) and the demonstration of the model assisted estimation. In order to enable evaluation of temporal consistency, the Vol, AGB and P_Con maps were produced also with 2024 satellite data. Estimates of uncertainty are, however, not yet available.

Another important point highlighted by Table 1 is that not all countries provided all forest attributes in their field reference datasets. The column “# countries” refers to the number of countries from which the plot data was available for mapping of the attribute in question. The measurement years of the plots used and the number of plots available for prediction of the different attributes are provided in Table 2. Separate feature banks have been compiled for each attribute with different sets of countries. This resulted in five feature banks for different sets of attributes (Table 2).

Table 1. Mapped attributes with key data characteristics.

Attribute	code	Unit	Years	# countries
Growing Stock Volume	Vol	m ³ /ha	2020 + 2024	14
Above Ground Biomass	AGB	t/ha	2020 + 2024	14
Conifer proportion (of AGB)	P_Con	% (of AGB)	2020 + 2024	14
Betula + Carpinus + Fraxinus	P_Bet_Car_Fra	% (of AGB)	2020	14
Populus and Salix	P_Pop_Sal	% (of AGB)	2020	14
Fagus	P_Fag	% (of AGB)	2020	14
Quercus	P_Que	% (of AGB)	2020	14
Eucalyptus	P_Euc	% (of AGB)	2020	14
Other_broadleaves	P_OthBL	% (of AGB)	2020	14
Picea	P_Pic	% (of AGB)	2020	14
Abies	P_Abi	% (of AGB)	2020	14
Pinus	P_Pin	% (of AGB)	2020	14
Other conifers	P_OthCon	% (of AGB)	2020	14
Quadratic mean diameter	DBH	cm	2020	12
Basal area	BA	m ² /ha	2020	9
Height	H	dm	2020	6
Gross annual increment (of AGB)	GAI	t/ha/a (x100)	2020	10
Net annual increment (of AGB)	NAI	t/ha/a (x100)	2020	10

Table 2. Number of NFI plots per feature bank (FB).

Country	Years	FB 1 (Vol, AGB, P_Con, PSp*)	FB 2 (DBH)	FB 3 (BA)	FB 4 (H)	FB 5 (GAI, NAI)
AT	2019-2022	5736	1482	1482	1482	1317
BE	2019-2021	1061	1061			499
CH	2019-2022	2624	2624	2624		2170
CZ	2019-2020	5017	5021	5022		2206
DE	2017	6186	6186	6186	6186	5799
ES	2018-2021	14326	14131	13765	13765	9098
FI	2020-2021	16545	16545	16545		
FR	2019-2021	15845	15845	15845	15845	
IE	2020-2022	1509	1509	1509	1509	1489
IT	2018-2019	6688	6656			6536
NO	2019-2021	7023	6574	6574	6574	6705
PL	2019-2021	18802				
SE	2019-2021	17300	17290			9568
SI	2018	736				
All		119398	94924	69552	45361	45387

* PSp = Proportions of 10 species groups.

Figure 1 illustrates the geographic availability of the NFI plots used for the mapping of the different attributes. It is worth noting the lack of plots from Southeastern Europe, and the limited coverage of plots for some attributes (particularly height). This needs to be taken into consideration when using the maps. Strictly speaking, the maps and the uncertainty estimates are only valid in areas where reference data were available. In all other areas the predictions may be biased as shown by Balazs et al. (in review).

Figure 1. Geographic distribution of reference plots in the five feature banks. Black outlines indicate Sentinel tiles with a size of 110 by 110 km.

Map uncertainties

The error metrics indicate high variation of the map uncertainties in different parts of Europe. Figure 2 provides an example of the distribution of error metrics for AGB across Europe. It can be seen that the RMSE ranges from the around 50 to 90%. Although in the great majority of areas the values are in the range of 50-70%, there are some pockets of over 90% RMSE. Similarly, bias varies from -6% to +5%, although on average the bias is close to zero. The R^2 sets the RMSE in relation to the variability in the field data. For AGB, it can be seen that while RMSE values in Central Europe are small relative to other parts of Europe, they are large relative to the variability of the field data (Figure 2). The maps of RMSE, bias and R^2 values for the key forest attributes are provided in Annex 1.

Figure 2. Example of map uncertainties: RMSE and Bias and R^2 of the AGB map.

The density scatter plots shown in Figure 3 include all NFI plots used and are thus not Sentinel-tile specific. The scatter plots for the key attributes indicate relatively good agreement between the predicted and observed values, with the known deficiencies of empirical regression methods. Some overestimation for small values can be seen in all of the attributes. The predictions saturate at higher values, causing underestimation in high value ranges. Density scatter plots for all attributes can be found in Annex 2. Note that the species proportion prediction uncertainties are generally high, particularly for species that tend to be in small minority throughout Europe (such as the *Populus-Salix* group).

Figure 3. Density scatter plots for key attributes: AGB, Volume, Height and Basal area.

Table 3 provides the error metrics calculated from the same reference datasets used to create the density scatter plots presented in Figure 3 and Annex 2. The RMSE values for the forest attributes (apart from tree species groups proportions) are on similar levels as have been reported in earlier studies with k-NN and 10-30 m resolution optical satellite data (Chirici et al. 2016). It is also important to note the relatively small biases for all the forest attributes on the level of Sentinel tiles. This is one of the strengths of the k-NN mapping approach. The R^2 values are also relatively high for the key forest attributes, which can also be seen as a good agreement in the density scatter plots. However, it has to be noted that these error metrics (like the density scatter plots) have been calculated using all NFI plots. The metrics and scatter plots for individual tiles show highly varying results (see Annex 1). For the tree species, the error metrics provide little information due to the drastically varying (and often low) proportions of the species in a given area, which complicates the interpretation of both the absolute and relative metrics. The density scatter plots (Annex 2) are considered the most informative source of error information for the species proportion maps.

Table 3. Error metrics calculated including all unique reference plots.

Attribute	RMSE	RMSE (%)	Bias	Bias%	R ²
Vol	137.78	69.53	1.57	0.79	0.42
AGB	85.58	67.45	0.82	0.64	0.36
P_Con	23.90	43.00	0.48	0.86	0.69
DBH	9.43	45.34	-0.09	-0.43	0.31
BA	12.11	53.85	0.06	0.27	0.37
H	49.31	31.23	0.19	0.12	0.63
GAI	276.88	78.75	-0.55	-0.16	0.50
NAI	270.13	80.53	-0.41	-0.12	0.49
P_Bet_Car_Fra	20.57	157.51	-0.25	-1.94	0.30
P_Pop_Sal	11.75	459.33	-0.37	-14.62	0.13
P_Fag	15.11	256.98	-0.02	-0.37	0.41
P_Que	21.01	140.10	0.55	3.65	0.56
P_Euc	1.76	3234.64	-0.01	-12.85	0.37
P_OthBL	18.85	239.76	-0.37	-4.71	0.22
P_Pic	22.00	114.39	-0.60	-3.14	0.54
P_Abi	8.06	484.82	-0.06	-3.68	0.37
P_Pin	25.58	78.72	1.20	3.69	0.61
P_OthCon	10.50	478.32	-0.05	-2.47	0.23

Limitations

A disadvantage of automatically generated tile-feature banks is that artifacts are more likely to occur in areas without NFI data compared to the region-wise feature banks that were used in Miettinen & Breidenbach et al. (2025). Due to the drastically changing tile feature banks, also the map predictions change which creates visible artifacts in the map. Figure 4 shows two artifacts in the 1) AGB (left) and GAI (right) maps.

Figure 4: Examples of map artifacts caused by drastic changes in the tile feature banks.

Another source of artifacts in the maps is the underlying satellite data (Figure 5). First, there are some no-data areas of varying sizes in the map. These can be caused by either a) unavailability of observations for the composite image creation or b) small gaps between the Sentinel-2 tiles used (as

some tiles were left out due to nearly complete overlap with adjacent tiles). In addition to the no-data areas, visible borders caused by a clear difference in the general level of the reflectance in two adjacent composite tiles can be seen between some tiles. These appear similar to the ones caused by the changing feature banks (Figure 4). The source of the border artifact can be identified by comparing the maps of different variables in the same area. If the artifact is present in all variables, it is likely due to the satellite data, but if it is visible only in some variables, it is caused by changes in the reference data.

Figure 5: Examples of map artifacts caused by satellite data. On the left, a large no-data area caused by the non-availability of high-quality imagery (central Sweden) and a slightly visible border at the bottom caused by differences in the levels of reflectance in two adjacent Sentinel-2 tiles. On the right, a narrow gap between the processed Sentinel-2 tiles (central Finland).

Map access and technical details

The PathFinder mapping and estimation platform output maps will become accessible through a specific dissemination module (web-GIS). While the dissemination module is under construction, the maps can be accessed from an SFTP server. Details will be provided upon request to jukka.miettinen@vtt.fi. In addition to all the map layers of attributes listed in Table 1, with corresponding standard deviation layers, the tile-wise error metrics (e.g., Figure 2) are also provided.

All the maps follow the same technical specifications listed in Table 4. For example, the standard deviation map of volume for the 500 x 500 km grid with the lower left corner E 3 900 000 m and N 2 400 000 m is '2020_stdev_vol_E39_N24.tif'. The grid structure is provided in Figure 6.

Table 4. Output map technical specifications.

Feature	Specification	Notes
Spatial resolution	10 m	Provided in 500 x 500 km tiles
Projection	EPSG:3035 -ETRS89-extended / LAEA Europe	
File naming	Final_demo_[YEAR]_[VAR]_E[xx]_N[yy].tif Final_demo_[YEAR]_stdev_[VAR]_E[xx]_N[yy].tif	[VAR] refers to Table 1 codes. [xx] and [yy] refer to lower left corner.
File format	UInt16	
Mask Values	32766: Non-forest 32767: No data	

Figure 6: Maps are provided in 10 m spatial resolution in 500 x 500 km tiles in the EPSG:3035 - ETRS89-extended / LAEA Europe projection.

Conclusion

The presented forest attribute maps are provided publicly at this point to allow open evaluation and gathering of feedback from the research community regarding the usability of the maps. It is important to emphasize, however, that the core concept of the European Forest Monitoring System prototype developed by PathFinder is not to use the maps as stand-alone products. Rather, the maps are intended to support model-assisted estimation, where model-related biases can be mitigated and field-based estimates enhanced. Pixel-counting estimates derived from the provided maps may be substantially biased, potentially leading to flawed outcomes if used to inform decision-making.

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Annex 1. Maps of tile-feature bank RMSE, bias and R²

Annex 2. Observed vs. predicted density scatter plots

